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Deterministic Assessment of the Variable Strut Inclination Method and Alternative Stirrup

Design Methods

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Abstract

The aim of developing an adequate and effective model for shear strength prediction has been the ultimate goal of a significant worldwide research effort. This contribution assessed the mean and design value predictions of shear models for beams with stirrups in current codes and published technical literature. The models investigated include the EC2 Variable Strut Inclination Method (VSIM) shear model, the simplified modified compression field theory (SMCFT) based *fib* Model Code 2010 shear level of approximation III, and the full modified compression field theory (MCFT). The mean and design value predictions from the various methods are compared to one another and to experimental results, over the parametric range of shear reinforcement, concrete strength and beam depth. The assessment revealed that the mean value predictions of the different models differ considerably from one another and experimental observations.

Keywords: reinforced concrete; shear resistance; shear reinforcement; design value analysis; mean value analysis

1 Introduction

The provisions of stirrup reinforcement in design is a vital design situation that frequently occurs in practice to prevent brittle failures in reinforced concrete beams. Most shear design procedures present shear capacity of reinforced concrete beams as the sum of the concrete and steel stirrups contributions, except for EC2 VSIM which only considers the steel contribution to shear resistance. Cladera & Mari [1] investigated the VSIM for stirrup design used in Eurocode 2 [2]. The outcomes showed that the VSIM predicts relatively high shear resistance for heavily shear reinforced concrete members and very low shear resistance for lightly shear reinforced concrete members. This trend of performance was also confirmed by others [3-6]. The inconsistent trend of the unbiased EC2 VSIM shear resistance predictions concerning the amount of shear reinforcement motivated the assessment of alternative shear approaches from current codes and published technical literature, which considers both the contribution of concrete and stirrup to shear resistance, across parametric ranges of main shear parameters.

It is noted that several recent studies have investigated the accuracy of different shear models for reinforced concrete beams with stirrups by using databases containing experimental beams failing due to different shear failure mechanisms [5, 7-10]. Some of the studies assessed the accuracy of shear models using databases containing experimental tests where some of the test shear failure mechanism differs from the theoretical failure mode predicted by the shear models under investigation. However, it is deemed essential to properly analyse the accuracy of shear strength models for shear reinforced concrete beams for individual contributing shear failure mechanism by using a database of experimental beams exclusively focused on the failure mechanism under consideration. Experimental test results of beams whose theoretical failure mode predicted by the model under investigation differ from the test failure mechanism will be eliminated from the database.

This contribution assesses the mean and design value predictions of shear resistance models for beams with stirrups in current codes and published technical literature using critically vetted database of experimental beams failing due to stirrup yielding only. The study is focused only on RC beam specimens failing in shear by yielding stirrups. Experimental test results of beams whose theoretical failure mode predicted by the model under investigation differ from the stirrup yielding mode of shear failure are eliminated from the database. The models investigated include the EC2 VSIM shear model [2], the simplified modified compression field theory (SMCFT) based *Fib* Model Code 2010 shear level of approximation III model (MC-10 (III)) [11] and the best-estimate prediction by full MCFT based

analysis program Response 2000 (R2k) [12]. A proper shear strength model is expected to reflect the trends depicted by the database of experimental results. The design value analysis is conducted to reveal the impact of the safety bias incorporated in the different shear design provisions.

2 Design and mean value function for the various shear methods

The estimation of design values for shear resistance models are based on characteristic values of material properties (f_{ck} , f_c' and f_{wk}) and partial safety factors for concrete γ_c and steel γ_s . The use of characteristic values for material properties and partial factors of safety introduces safety bias into the design formulation. The safety bias reduces the unbiased or best estimate resistance (mean value) prediction of the model under investigation.

The design shear resistance (V_{Rd}) of a reinforced concrete member with shear reinforcement is described as the sum of the concrete ($V_{Rd,c}$) and shear reinforcement contributions ($V_{Rd,s}$) [5, 7, 13].

$$V_{Rd} = V_{Rd,c} + V_{Rd,s} \leq V_{Rd,max} \quad (1)$$

It is considered that the shear strength V_{Rd} in (1) above must be lower than the shear force that produces failure in the concrete struts ($V_{Rd,max}$). $V_{Rd,max}$ represents a check aimed at preventing the occurrence of another failure mode, namely concrete strut failure.

The mean value function for each shear method is obtained by, where applicable, expressing f_{ck} , f_c' and f_{wk} at their mean values f_{cm} and f_{ywm} , respectively and removing all explicit partial safety factors (γ_c and γ_s) from the original formulation. Eurocode 2 [2] recommend the relationship presented in (2) for obtaining the mean value for concrete strength. f_{ck} is the characteristic cylinder strength and a 5% fractile value.

$$f_{cm} = f_{ck} + 8 \text{ MPa} \quad (2)$$

Holicky [14] reports the following relationship presented in (3) for obtaining the mean value for steel yield strength.

$$f_{ywm} = f_{yw} + 2\sigma_{fyw} \quad (3)$$

where $\sigma_{fyw} = 0.1f_{yw}$ is the standard deviation of steel yield strength as observed from standard European steel production practice.

2.1 Eurocode 2 VSIM design shear resistance [2]

According to Eurocode 2, the design of beams with stirrups is based on the Variable Strut Inclination method (VSIM), for which the strut angle θ (5) is restricted to the range of $21.8^\circ \leq \theta_d \leq 45^\circ$. The shear strength is due to the resistance of the stirrups (4).

$$V_{Rd,s} = \frac{A_{sw}}{s} z f_{ywd} \cot \theta_d \quad (4)$$

$$\theta_d = \sin^{-1} \sqrt{\frac{A_{sw} f_{ywd}}{b_w s v_1 \alpha_{cc} f_{cd}}} \quad (5)$$

where A_{sw} is the cross-sectional area of the shear reinforcement. s denotes the spacing of the stirrups. f_{ywd} and f_{cd} represent the design values of the steel yield strength and concrete compressive cylinder strength, respectively. θ_d is the design concrete strut angle. The value of v_1 maybe taken to be 0.6 for $f_{ck} \leq 60$ MPa and as $0.9 - \frac{f_{ck}}{200}$ for high-strength concrete beams. The internal lever arm may be taken as $z = 0.9d$. The coefficient factor accounting for long term effects on concrete was assigned

a mean value of $\alpha_{cc} = 0.85$ [15]. The coefficient accounting for the state of stress in the compression chord is represented by α_{cw} . γ is the partial factor for steel and concrete, X_k is the characteristic value.

2.2 Full experimental database

A database of 160 tests on slender beams with stirrup failure compiled by Reineck et al. [16] is used in this study. The evaluation database consists of simply supported rectangular and flanged beams subjected to point loads. The maximum longitudinal reinforcement ratio is employed at midspan of the beams in the region of the maximum bending moment and not at the supports where the moment is much smaller. The shear span to depth ratio, (a/d) , of the beams, is greater than 2.40. The beams failed predominantly by diagonal tension and shear compression. Experimental tests with the flexural mode of failure were excluded from the database. The evaluation database covers a wide range of design situations ranging from low to high amount of shear reinforcement, and small, ordinary and large effective depths. Beams ranging from low to high concrete strength are also included. In general, the highest number of data points in the database are found in the smaller size range and lower amount of shear reinforcement.

3 VSIM mean value predictions compared to MCFT and experimental observation

The plot of normalised experimental observations ($V^{exp}/b_w d$) from the database with the amount of shear reinforcement $\rho_w f_{yw} m$ is presented in Fig. 1. Most of the experimental beams presented in Section 2.2 are crowded in the range of low amount of shear reinforcement and smaller size. As shown in the figure, the trend line of the mean shear capacity ($V^m/b_w d$) predictions offered by EC2 VSIM is compared to trend lines of normalised experimental observations and MCFT (R2k) predictions.

Fig. 1 Comparison of normalised VSIM mean shear capacity to MCFT and experimental observations

An increasing trend of normalised experimental observations ($V^{exp}/b_w d$) as $\rho_w f_{yw}$ increases was observed in Fig. 1. The trend lines of MCFT predictions bear the closest comparison to that of the experimental observations for the range of shear reinforcement $\rho_w f_{yw}$ considered.

VSIM shear method provided lower capacity predictions over the parametric range compared to other shear methods, with VSIM providing the most conservative predictions at $\rho_w f_{yw} < 1 \text{ MPa}$. The lower capacity predictions of VSIM at $\rho_w f_{yw} < 1 \text{ MPa}$ can be attributed to the neglect of concrete contribution to shear resistance which is more significant in lightly shear reinforced beams [6]. The trend line of VSIM fails to capture the trend of experimental observations at higher levels of shear reinforcement $\rho_w f_{yw}$, portraying a relatively reducing contribution of additional stirrup reinforcement. This trend of results for the VSIM model agrees with the observation reported in [4] which is attributed to the limitation imposed on the concrete strut angle. The design concrete strut angle θ_d predicted by VSIM at this region exceeds the lower limit of 21.8° .

4 Parametric assessment

Parametric analysis of specific test sections was used to EC2 evaluate mean and design values at practical ranges of shear reinforcement and concrete strength. These are representative test sections obtained by choosing representative combinations of the most vital shear parameters within the allowable limits of EC2 specifications. The test sections are distinguished by their $\rho_w f_{yw} \cdot f_{cm}$ and beam depth d . The concrete strength f_{cm} and amount of stirrup reinforcement $\rho_w f_{yw}$ are considered each at low and high representative values. The traditional beam setup with a single central point load on simple supports was assumed for longitudinal geometry.

4.1 Results of the mean value assessment

The normalised mean value predictions ($V_m/b_w d$) provided by the different best estimate procedures versus the amount of shear reinforcement $\rho_w f_{yw}$ are shown in Fig. 2 and 3 for low concrete strength ($f_{cm} = 30 \text{ MPa}$) and high concrete strength ($f_{cm} = 80 \text{ MPa}$), respectively. The test sections have the following properties: $b_w = 350$, $d = 650 \text{ mm}$, $a/d = 2.5$, $\rho_l = 4\%$. Selected series of experimental tests in the region of low ($24 \leq f_{cm} < 35 \text{ MPa}$) and high concrete strength ($70 \leq f_{cm} < 87 \text{ MPa}$) from the experimental database were added for interest's sake. The selected series of experimental tests have a wide range of different dimensions and cannot be directly compared to the capacity predictions from the specific test sections. According to the observations from other researchers [12, 9] later confirmed in Fig. 1, the MCFT (R2k) trend line bears the closest comparison to that of the experimental observations out of the shear methods investigated. Hence, in this analysis, MCFT (R2k) observations were assumed to best reflect the shear behaviour for the specific test sections considered.

Fig. 2 Normalised mean predictions of shear capacity versus the amount of shear reinforcement $\rho_w f_{yw m}$ for $f_{cm} = 30$ MPa

Fig. 3 Normalised mean predictions of shear capacity versus the amount of shear reinforcement $\rho_w f_{yw m}$ for $f_{cm} = 80$ MPa

Scrutiny of Fig. 2 and 3 reveal that VSIM predicts consistently more conservative values at low levels of shear reinforcement than other shear methods. All the models considered diverge from the MCFT (R2k) predictions, as shown in Fig. 2 and 3. It can be observed that the shear strength prediction from the different shear models differs widely. The fundamental difference between the different shear methods is that they have been derived from different theories, analogies and assumptions, emphasising

the contribution of different shear transfer mechanisms and governing parameters [5]. Mari *et al.* [5] further stated that various shear strength contributors act at different stages of loading. This illustrates the difficulty in predicting shear resistance of reinforced concrete beams reliably.

4.2 Results of the design value assessment

The normalised design value resistance predictions ($V_{Rd}/b_w d$) obtained from the different design approaches for the design range of stirrup reinforcement $\rho_w f_{ywd}$ and concrete strength f_{cd} considered are presented in Fig. 4 and 5. Selected series of experimental observations are added for interest's sake. The experimental observations have a wide range of different dimensions and cannot be compared directly to design values. Note that MCFT (R2k) predictions are not considered in the design value assessment since they are not design methods but rather best-estimate procedures. The test sections investigated have the following characteristics: $b_w = 150$, $d = 350$ mm, $a/d = 2.5$, $\rho_l = 3\%$.

Fig. 4 Normalised design value shear strength versus the amount of shear reinforcement $\rho_w f_{ywd}$ for $f_{ck} = 22$ MPa

Fig. 4 Normalised design value shear strength versus the amount of shear reinforcement $\rho_w f_{ywd}$ for $f_{ck} = 72$ MPa

Analysis of Fig. 4 and 5 revealed that the design values of the different formulations generally compare well, except for VSIM at low levels of shear reinforcement. EC2 VSIM design method is the most conservative method at low levels of shear reinforcement ($\rho_w f_{ywd} < 1$ MPa) for both low ($f_{ck} = 22$ MPa) and high ($f_{ck} = 72$ MPa) concrete strengths.

5 Conclusions

This contribution compares the mean and design value predictions from different shear methods to one another and to experimental results, over the parametric range of shear reinforcement and concrete strength. The models investigated include the EC2 VSIM shear model, the Fib Model Code 2010 (MC-10 (III)) shear model and the best-estimate prediction by Modified Compression Field Theory (MCFT) based analysis program Response 2000 (R2k). The mean value analysis was conducted to provide a general overview of the performance of the unbiased capacity predictions from the models and provide a solid basis to assess their accuracy. The design value analysis was carried out to reveal the impact of the safety bias incorporated in the different shear design provisions.

The assessment revealed that the mean value predictions of the different models differ considerably from one another. This reflects the difficulty of accurately and precisely predicting shear resistance in structural design. The capacity predictions from the different methods also differ from experimental observations. The mean value predictions from MCFT (R2k) predictions bear the closest comparison to that of the experimental observations for the range of shear reinforcement $\rho_w f_{ywm}$ investigated. The mean value predictions of the EC2 VSIM was shown to significantly underpredict capacity for slightly shear-reinforced concrete beams. The shear method produced the most conservative mean value predictions out of all the methods investigated at $\rho_w f_{ywm} \leq 1$ MPa.

The design value analysis revealed that the design values of the various shear design methods compare well, except for EC2 VSIM at low levels of shear reinforcement ($\rho_w f_{ywd} \leq 1$ MPa) where the design method significantly underestimates the capacity for beams with both low and high concrete

strengths. The trend of EC2 VSIM at low levels of stirrup reinforcement practically implies that the design method may be overly conservative at this region, and therefore uneconomic. This is an issue of concern.

The inability of the different shear strength models to accurately capture trends witnessed from experimental observations and also, the differences in predictions from the different models attests to the presence of significant model uncertainties. The extent of scattering of the various curves reveals the wide-spread uncertainty and problems associated with predicting shear resistance of beams. The uncertainty composed of the uncertainty inherent in the shear resistance model formulations and uncertainty in the prediction of the mean values of their basic variables such as concrete strength and steel yield strength. Given the significant uncertainties present in shear strength predictions, reliability performance assessment and calibration of suitable partial factors for shear design procedures become essential. This will allow us to adequately account for the effects of these uncertainties and ensure safe and economical application of shear design procedures in practice.

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